

Ephemeral Interactive Computing for NASA Communities

Interactive computing is changing workflows [1] for collaborative science. This evolution, driven by technological and social innovations, provokes a reimagining of science at grand scale. The unification [2] of federal agencies to declare **2023** as the **Year of Open Science** makes now the right time to build the new technologies, set the interoperability standards, and define the social collaboration structures necessary for a new era of *open-source science*. We propose to **launch ephemeral interactive computing services for NASA** that will:

1. Improve shareability and reproducibility of scientific information,
2. Broaden participation by historically excluded and under-resourced communities in science,
3. Enable interactive computing activities (hackathons, demonstrations, training programs) during workshops and conferences.

These outcomes will be achieved by deploying and operating persistent “binder” services with access and scope controls designed for usage scenarios by NASA communities.

Jupyter Ecosystem

The open source [Jupyter](#) ecosystem is used widely by NASA communities and throughout science [3]. The ecosystem includes the classic Jupyter notebook, the integrated developer environment [JupyterLab](#), and the system for creating and sharing books and articles from computational materials called [Jupyter Book](#) [4]. Jupyter can be deployed locally on personal computers for single user usage. Jupyter (and other resources such as RStudio, [QGIS](#), and Linux machines in a browser tab) can also be deployed on the cloud for usage by multiple users with persistent storage using [JupyterHub](#). Ephemeral interactive computing sessions with a curated software environment and a target code repository, hosted on the cloud without persistent storage, can be launched through [binder service](#) using [BinderHub](#) deployed on the cloud. Ephemeral interactive computing sessions, hosted inside an individual’s browser, can be launched using the emerging [JupyterLite](#).

Open-source science is enabled when the components of the Jupyter ecosystem are coherently deployed, operated and managed for NASA’s and other scientific communities. Example communities like [Pangeo](#), [CryoCloud](#), [WIFIRE](#), [GWOSC](#) and many more showcase how curated toolchains deployed, operated and managed on the cloud and adjacent to research data are advancing on NASA’s open-source science goals. The passive availability of components as open source software is not enough to support vibrant scientific communities. Real advances on NASA’s goals for open-source science require active integration, curation and ongoing management of the computational and data services required by scientific communities.

We propose to enrich the interactive computing ecosystem for NASA communities by deploying a “big binder” service with large compute resources and with access restricted to

user accounts on an allow-list controlled by NASA and a “public binder” service restricted to launch sessions from an allow-list of code repositories controlled by NASA.

Binder mobilizes knowledge

[Mybinder.org](https://mybinder.org) is an open service to provide reproducible interactive computing environments for research, education, and data science. It is run using open source infrastructure from [the Jupyter project](https://jupyter.org), and is managed by a team of volunteers spread across a [federated of BinderHubs](https://binderhub.org). This proposal builds on the founding vision for binder described in [5]. For more information about mybinder.org, see [the Binder Documentation](https://mybinder.org/docs).

The largest member of the Binder federation is gke.mybinder.org, which runs on Google Kubernetes Engine. This infrastructure runs on credit allotments from Google Research, and costs roughly \$8,000-9,000 a month (or, around \$.01 per user session).

Mybinder.org serves around 200,000 interactive user sessions a week (and gke.mybinder.org makes up about 70% of this amount, or 140,000 sessions a week). A user session is when a person clicks a “Binder link” and generates an interactive computing session where they can explore the content defined in a Binder repository. Mybinder.org served more than **8,000,000** interactive sessions during 2021.

Part of the Binder Project’s mission is to make reproducible interactive computing more accessible to the global community by leveraging cloud infrastructure. Mybinder.org serves a global community of researchers and users, and in 2021 has served sessions to individuals from every single country in the world.

Global impact of mybinder.org. (left) User sessions globally in 2021. (middle) Monthly user sessions by continent. (right) Monthly user sessions by gross region.

Mybinder.org enables under-resourced and historically excluded communities to access state-of-the-art, but relatively small, interactive computing resources. NASA can use the “big binder” approach proposed here to complement the smaller Mybinder.org service by providing larger ephemeral computing resources to authorized users. Some usage scenarios will be described below.

Tension: Open vs. Sustainable

Mybinder.org’s initial design was open-by-default. *Anyone* with access to the internet could form a binder link and launch interactive computing sessions with on-the-fly software environments and code from *arbitrary* public repositories and consume cloud computing resources provided by the Binder Federation. This open-by-default approach was altered to an [open-but-no-crypto](#) approach when it was determined that binder was being used for cryptocurrency mining. Federation members did not invest in cloud resources for binder to support cryptocurrency mining so Binder implemented systems to block those kinds of sessions.

The current Mybinder.org approach to delivering binder-as-a-service enables interested stakeholders to contribute cloud credits to support a universal ephemeral interactive computing service that can be launched by anyone on the internet. Some organizations, with an interest in binder, may not wish to invest to support sessions by people outside their community or to support sessions involving content outside the organization’s area of interest. Federation members may not wish for their funds to be used for sessions with large computing resources. These disincentives – don’t want to pay for everyone, don’t want to pay for sessions with content outside of the organization’s interest area, don’t want to pay costs for large cloud computing resource scenarios – are obstacles to delivering sustainable ephemeral interactive computing for open-source science. This proposal explores a binder-as-a-service delivery model with improved potential for long-term sustainability through better alignment of incentives using scope controls.

The scope-controlled binder services we propose here enable NASA to *target investment* for NASA-focused ephemeral interactive computing that provides sessions:

1. with larger computing resources (“big binder for NASA users”) than is available through Mybinder.org to users in an **allow-list of users** controlled by NASA and affiliates;
2. with small computing resources (“public binder for NASA content”) for content in an **allow-list of code repositories** controlled by NASA and affiliates (such as [Openscapes](#)).

The new service delivery models – more compute for a specified audience; publicly accessible small compute for specific content – allow for improved sharing of NASA content within, among, by, and for NASA communities. The improved binder services we will build, deploy and operate for NASA confront disincentives in the Mybinder.org approach to sustainably fund ephemeral computing services using a more federated approach through targeted investment. Benefits of federation were anticipated by the originators of binder [5].

Service Plan

We will improve and contribute to the [upstream BinderHub code base](#) and in collaboration with the associated open source community. This approach ensures that other communities can replicate the binder infrastructure we build using funds from NASA. Building on ongoing discussions and development in this community, we will improve **scope controls** to BinderHub, the software that underpins the binder service:

1. **User allow-list.** Improve the access gateway in BinderHub to enable NASA personnel to restrict session launches to a list of allowed users.
2. **Repository allow-list.** Improve BinderHub's capacity to restrict session launches to a list of allowed repositories managed by NASA personnel.

We will supplement the [Mybinder.org link generator](#) to include the option to specify the binder hub in analogy with the way [nbgitpuller allows to specify the JupyterHub](#). This change will enable creation of binder links that launch sessions on a specified binder hub instead of default launching on Mybinder.org.

We will deploy two new binder services:

1. A “**big binder for NASA users**” that provides larger compute resources and is accessible by users in the *User allow-list* managed by NASA;
2. A “**public binder for NASA content**” that provides compute resources similar to what is offered via Mybinder.org, is publicly accessible, and will only launch sessions from repositories in the *Repository allow-list* managed by NASA.

We propose to deploy these services in the Amazon Web Services us-west-2 (Oregon) region data center adjacent to many data sets used by NASA communities. We have the capability to launch binder services on Google Cloud, AWS, and Microsoft Azure and can adapt plans in consultation with NASA. We **budget** \$1K/month for the PI, \$3K/month for engineering, and just under \$900/month for admin support. We budget \$1,250/month in cloud costs for each binder service. Over twelve months, and with 10% overhead, this creates a total budget of \$97,500. Our service will include monitoring and paying for ongoing cloud computing costs. Improvements we develop through this engagement with NASA to the BinderHub **software will be shared upstream** so that other communities can benefit from our work with NASA. NASA engagement will be carried out by PI, CO-I1, CO-I2, CG1. Deployment and ongoing operations will be carried out by CO-I1, E1, E2, E3, E4, and E5.

Usage Scenarios

The proposed scope control improvements diversify the usage scenarios for the binder service and enable experimentation with new business models for sustainable open-source science. We describe some example scenarios:

1. NASA may wish to enable ephemeral interactive computing sessions that supplement and enrich NASA's Visualization, Exploration and Data Analysis Project ([NASA VEDA](#)). In current form, the Mybinder.org service supported with cloud credits assembled through the Binder Federation launches interactive sessions from arbitrary repositories, and not just those repositories linked to VEDA. The ability to restrict session launches to repositories identified by VEDA allows NASA to target the use of funds for binder.
2. Imagine a student from San Joaquin Delta College, an [AANAPSI, HSI](#) college in Stockton California, clicks a VEDA binder link on [data-backed wildfire modeling](#) to

launch a “public binder for NASA content” session and gets excited to investigate more but she needs more computing power. Since San Joaquin Delta College is part of the [NASA Community College Network](#) and NCCN offers a “big binder service” with access granted to students in this network, she has access to a more powerful service and uses it to carry out deeper work. Ongoing exploration inspired by this experience leads the student to a career in climate change mitigation.

3. Suppose NASA’s Living with a Star ([LWS](#)) Program wishes to convene a multi-stakeholder workshop with interactive computational narratives focused on power grid resiliency to solar weather events. The narratives intertwine solar weather and power grid models and involve larger data and more compute resources than can be sustainably provided by the Mybinder.org service. The workshop participants include scientists, policymakers, and energy industry personnel. The ability to replicate the binder service while restricting access to an allowed list of users creates the opportunity for NASA to address the requirements of the workshop and build effective research-to-operations-to-research information flows. The “big binder” service with an allow-list of users enables NASA to provide this audience with access to powerful ephemeral compute resources with a focus on power grid resiliency to space weather events.
4. Suppose NASA wishes to enable improved sharing of computational narratives among the various [Distributed Active Archive Centers \(DAACs\)](#). Imagine that recent advances made in [NOAA’s National Oceanography Data Center \(NODC\)](#) provide insights that should be rapidly shared with the [National Snow and Ice Data Center \(NSIDC\)](#) and the [Global Hydrometeorology Research Center](#). The “big binder for NASA Communities” provides a rich interactive channel for sharing computational narratives that describe NODC’s advance with NSIDC and GHRC experts. The “big binder” service becomes the glue that intertwines the DAACs into a more responsive network for Earth system observation and ongoing management.
5. Suppose the American Geophysical Union ([AGU](#)) wishes to launch a new format journal that delivers peer reviewed reproducible and interactive journal articles delivered via binder. AGU wants to provide free and open access to “small binder” sessions rendering AGU content with small compute resources to anyone on the internet and “big binder” access with larger compute resources to paid subscribers. The proposed improvements to allow restriction to an allowed list of content repositories and an allowed list of subscribers who can access the “big binder” enables this scenario. This last scenario begins to show how scope-controlled ephemeral computing services enable new business models that advance open-source science.

These scenarios reveal how the proposed improvements to BinderHub enable granular control of costs and usage scope, and enrich the capacity to broadcast interactive content for open-source science. The scenarios indicate that these improvements may launch new business models and co-investments supporting open science from publishers, funding agencies, and other stakeholders.

We request HPOSS funding to allow us to improve, deploy and operate ephemeral interactive computing services for NASA using binder. These services support broader participation in science, mobilize knowledge, enable new forms of collaboration and advance toward the goals of the NASA Open-Source Science Initiative.

References

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- [2] “FACT SHEET: Biden-Harris Administration Announces New Actions to Advance Open and Equitable Research | OSTP,” *The White House*, Jan. 11, 2023. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/news-updates/2023/01/11/fact-sheet-biden-harris-administration-announces-new-actions-to-advance-open-and-equitable-research/> (accessed Feb. 03, 2023).
- [3] J. M. Perkel, “Why Jupyter is data scientists’ computational notebook of choice,” *Nature*, vol. 563, no. 7729, pp. 145–146, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1038/d41586-018-07196-1.
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Open-Source Science Development Plan

The proposed project builds on prior open source software and infrastructure-as-code developed by and with contributors to the Jupyter ecosystem and, in particular, BinderHub. We will launch, operate, and manage ephemeral interactive computing platforms using BinderHub deployed on commercially available cloud computing infrastructure. New “big binder” service with access restricted to user accounts specified by NASA will offer larger compute resources than is currently available through Mybinder.org. New “public binder” service with scope restricted to code repositories specified by NASA will enrich NASA’s open-source science and public engagement efforts.

Software development, licensing and upstream contributions

Any contributions we make to the Jupyter and binder ecosystem will be shared following best practices within the aligned open source communities. We commit that:

- Our conduct while working on this project will be consistent with the [Project Jupyter Code of Conduct](#) and [NASA SMD Code of Conduct](#). We welcome collaboration.
- Software we develop [will be licensed](#) under the [BSD-3-Clause license](#) and openly shared through publicly accessible code repositories.
- Improvements we develop will be shared via pull-request into the upstream [BinderHub project on GitHub](#) (or in other publicly accessible version controlled repositories as appropriate).

Open-Source Science Infrastructure Plan

Our proposed project uses software and commercially available cloud computing resources to launch, operate, and manage ephemeral interactive computing platforms for use by NASA communities. When deployed and in operational use by science communities, these platforms are *science infrastructure*, a category that requires additional considerations beyond *science software* to achieve the goals of open-source science. We commit that:

- The binder services we deploy, operate, and manage for NASA will use infrastructure-as-code that is interoperable across Google Cloud, Amazon Web Services, and Microsoft Azure.
- The methods we use to deploy, operate and manage binder services for NASA will be designed and shared so that NASA and others can replicate the services.
 - We must only use open source software that is freely available to everyone on the same terms to define the infrastructure so that others can replicate the infrastructure without requiring special relationships with proprietary software vendors.
 - We must not directly depend upon proprietary cloud-vendor-specific software, products, tools or APIs. Instead, we use open-source methods to manage commercial cloud resources interoperably.
 - We encourage but do not require that NASA and others that use this infrastructure use open source software. The infrastructure must be delivered using open source software but the tools delivered using this infrastructure can include proprietary or closed-source software.

- These commitments to replicability and interoperability ensure that ephemeral interactive computing can be delivered using commercially available cloud computing resources while avoiding lock-in to any particular commercial cloud vendor.
- These commitments to replicability and interoperability provide an alternate service continuity plan for NASA and others.
- The binder services we will deploy, operate and manage for NASA enable sharing of computational narratives within, for, and by NASA communities.

Ongoing Commitment to Openness

We believe that our open-source science development plan ensures that our project will be in compliance with NASA policies and guidance, including:

- [SPD41a](#)
- [Open Source Science Guidance](#)
- [Software Management and Sharing](#)
- [ESDS Open Source Software Policy](#)

We are committed to open-source science and will adapt and improve our practices as we move forward in the project.

We view our commitments to providing interoperable, replicable, and vendor-agnostic science infrastructure as flowing from a fundamental human right to participate in science.